

A Review on Novel Drug Delivery System Nanoemulsion

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ABSTRACT: various researcher are innovate a replacement therapy regarding improvement of drug action. Improve drugs absorption, distribution also we improve its efficacy. Amongst that a replacement innovative technology are develops. A nanoemulsion is technique to enhance the solubility, bioavailability, pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamics of medicine. In this review article we familiar about the novel technique nanoemulsion and its preparation methods, characterization of nanoemulsion. Nanoemulsion has been identified as a promising delivery system for various drugs including biopharmaceuticals. Nanoemulsion may be a heterogeneous system composed of one immiscible liquid dispersed as droplets within another liquid. The droplet size of nano emulsion is between 20 to 500 nm. Diameter and surface properties of droplets of nanoemulsion plays a crucial role in the biological behavior of the formulation. Small droplet sizes cause transparent emulsions so that product appearance is not altered by the addition of an oil phase during this paper various aspects of nanoemulsion have been discussed including advantages, disadvantages and methods of preparation. Furthermore new approaches of stability of formulation, effect of types and concentration of surfactant, process variables and method also are discussed to improve the stability of nanoemulsion formulation.

KEYWORDS: Nanoemulsion, types, solubility, efficacy.

INTRODUCTION

An novel system of drug delivery may fulfill with aim of reducing toxicity and increasing efficacy. With the progress in time and advances in science and technology, dosage forms have evolved from simple mixtures and pills, to highly sophisticated systems, which are referred to as novel drug delivery systems. One among the examples of novel drug delivery system is nanoemulsions [1]. The nanoemulsion are defined as thermodynamically stable, isotropically clear dispersion of two immiscible liquids like oil and water, stabilized by an interfacial film of surfactant molecule [2]. Nanoemulsion is emulsion with uniform and very small droplet size in the range of 20-200 nm [3]. Nanoemulsions don't form spontaneously; to rupture larger droplets into smaller ones, external shear must be applied. As we compared to micro emulsion phases, relatively little is understood about creating and controlling nano-emulsions. Nanoparticles have a number of physicochemical and physiological characteristics that make them particularly suitable materials for these applications, which are related to their small particle size and high surface area. [4]

STRUCTURE OF NANOEMULSIONS

Nanoemulsions consist of a dispersion of small droplets of one immiscible liquid in another immiscible liquid [5]. The two immiscible liquids most widely used in commercial applications are oil and water, so for the purpose nanoemulsions are in form of oil-in-water (O/W) or the water-in-oil (W/O) type (fig).

simple emulsion o/w and w/o emulsion

complex emulsion o/w/o and w/o/w emulsion

O/ W nanoemulsions contains of small oil particles drops dispersed in an aqueous medium, whereas W/ O nanoemulsions correspond of small water droplets dispersed in an oleaginous medium(6). O/ W nanoemulsions are far more generally utilized than W/ O ones, and thus, they're going to be the major focus of this book. The droplets in O/ W nanoemulsions are generally carpeted by a hydrophilic emulsifier, whereas those in W/ O nanoemulsions are covered by a lipophilic emulsifier. The character of the emulsifier present at the oil- water interface plays a critical role in determining the overall functional attributes of nanoemulsions and should be precisely selected for each specific operation.

O/ W nanoemulsions are frequently used as templates to make other types of structured nanoparticle dispersion. Solid lipid nanoparticles(SLNs) and nanostructured lipid carriers(NLCs) correspond of fully or partly crystalline lipid particles dispersed in an aqueous medium, respectively Typically, an O/ W nanoemulsion is initially formed by homogenizing a high- melting lipid and an aqueous phase containing a hydrophilic surfactant at a temperature above the freezing point of the lipid. The system is additionally cooled below the lipid phase melting point, which ends up in the crystallization of the oil droplets. The solidified lipid introduce SLNs and NLCs retards molecular diffusion processes, which are useful for inhibiting the chemical degradation or controlling the discharge of encapsulated substances. The physical state of the lipid droplets can also alter the density and refractive index, which may change the creaming stability and optical properties of nanoemulsions. Other sorts of structures can also be produced using nanoemulsions as building blocks, including multiple emulsions of the water-in-oil-in-water (W/O/W) or oil-in-water-in-oil (O/W/O) type .These systems are usually produced employing a two-step process For example, a W/O/W emulsion is produced by initially forming a W/O nanoemulsion by homogenizing a water phase with an oil phase containing a lipophilic surfactant together, and then, this nanoemulsion is homogenized with a water phase containing a hydrophilic surfactant. Multiple emulsions have advantages surely applications, like protecting a hydrophilic substance from the external aqueous phase, controlling the discharge of a hydrophilic substance, reducing the off-flavor of a hydrophilic substance (such as bitterness or astringency), or reducing the general fat content of the system .

Nanoemulsions also can be used as building blocks for other types of structures, like filled hydrogels . during this case, an O/W nanoemulsion is mixed with a biopolymer solution that's capable of forming a hydrogel, and then, a two-step process is employed to form the filled hydrogels, particle formation and particle gelation. Initially, a particle is made that contains small lipid droplets trapped inside a larger biopolymer-rich water droplet, then the system conditions are changed to cross-link the biopolymers within the water droplet.Filled hydrogels are often designed to encapsulate, protect, and release bio- active components by altering their dimensions, internal composition, or structure. This will be achieved by altering the fabrication method used and the type and concentration of biopolymer and cross-linking agents used. additionally, the properties of the lipid droplets trapped inside the hydrogels also can be controlled, like their size, concentration, composition, or charge.

Nanoemulsions also can be used to create other types of structures such as colloidosomes or microclusters . A colloidosome consists of an outsized central particle with smaller particles adsorbed to its surface, whereas a micro- cluster consists of variety of smaller particles held together by attractive forces. These sorts of structures may be created from nanoemulsions in order to change the rheological, optical, or stability properties of materials or for controlled release applications.

ADVANTAGES OF NANOEMULSION

- It gives site specific delivery of medicine
- Nanoemulsion has capacity to dissolve large quantities of hydrophobics
- Ability to guard drugs from degradation with long term stability which leads to making an ideal drug delivery system [6]
- This could also be used as substitute for the vesicles and liposomes
- It is non-irritant and non-toxic
- This are wont to improves the bioavailability of drug
- It provide greater absorption because have small-sized droplets having greater area
- It is feasible to formulate it in variety of formulations i.e., as creams, liquids, foams, and sprays
- This is additionally used in taste masking
- In cell culture technology it provides better uptake of oil-soluble supplements [7]

DISADVANTAGES OF NANOEMULSIONS

- It requires large concentration of surfactant and cosurfactant for stabilizing the nanodroplets
- It generally shows a limited solubilizing capacity for high-melting substances
- There is lacuna for understanding the interfacial chemistry which is involved in production of nanoemulsions
- For use in pharmaceutical applications the character of surfactant must be nontoxic
- It requires the utilization of high concentrations of emulsifiers [8,9]

MECHANISM OF NANO EMULSION SYSTEM

The entropy changes which favor the dispersion is bigger than the energy that required to increase the surface of dispersion due to this free energy of conventional emulsion is direct function of energy is required to create new surface between oil and water phase and the addition of emulsifying agent to reduce the interfacial tension and because of this emulsion is stabilized [10-13].

Application of nanoemulsion

Nanoemulsion has become a really attractive formulation for the delivery of pharmaceuticals. Nanoemulsion also shows an honest advantage in the field of cosmetics. The attraction of nanoemulsion formulation in pharmaceuticals and cosmetics is thanks to following reasons.

Nanoemulsion never shows the creaming and sedimentation quite problems thanks to its very small droplet size. These problems are quite common with conventional emulsion and even microemulsion. Basically both problems are associated with the influence of gravitational force over the droplet of emulsion. But just in case of nanoemulsion the droplet size is very small which minimized the working of gravitational force over the droplets and possess creaming and sedimentation of emulsion.

• Again small droplet size of nanoemulsion prevents the coalescence of droplets. In the coalescence process droplets come together and form a large droplet with increased size which is responsible for the instability of emulsion. But the small droplet size of nanoemulsion prevent the coalescence among them and prevent the deformation and than surface fluctuation.

• Dispersibility of nanoemulsion is extremely high as compared to microemulsion because small droplet size prevents the flocculation of droplets and this process makes the system dispersed without separation.

• Nanoemulsion formulation provides a rapid penetration of active ingredients through skin thanks to the large surface area of droplets. Even sometimes it's found that nanoemulsion penetrate easily through rough skin. This property of nanoemulsion minimizes the extra utilization of special penetration enhancer which is responsible for incompatibility of formulation.

• Nanoemulsion formulation required low amount of surfactant compared to microemulsion. for instance about 20- 25 % surfactant is required for the preparation of microemulsion but 5-10 % surfactant is sufficient in case of nanoemulsion. Again with the assistance of nanoemulsion surfactant utilization can be minimized.

• Nanoemulsion features a transparent and fluidy property which improves the formulation patient compliance and safe for administration due to the absence of any thickening agent and colloidal particles.

• It is additionally reported that nanoemulsion may be used for the target delivery of active ingredient especially in cancer therapy.

• Nanoemulsion formulation may become the stable alternative for the liposomes and vesicle sort of delivery systems.

• Nanoemulsion formulation are often administered by the various routes of body. There are various reported methods which support the administration of nanoemulsion formulation through parenteral , oral , topical , nasal and ocular route.

• These formulations could also be used to increase the bioavailability of poor water soluble drug by developing oil in water type of nanoemulsion [14-28].

PREPARATION METHODS OF NANOEMULSION

Several methods are suggested for the preparation of nanoemulsion. the essential objectives of the nanoemulsion preparation to realize the droplet size range of 100-600 nm and another is to provide the stability condition. Formation of nanoemulsion system required a high amount of energy. This energy are often provided either by mechanical equipment or the chemical potential inherent within the component [29]. Here some methods are discussed which are freely used for the nanoemulsion preparation.

1. Phase inversion method

In this method fine dispersion is obtained by chemical energy resulting of phase transitions taking place through emulsification path. The adequate phase transitions are produced by varying the composition at constant temperature or by varying the temperature at constant composition, phase inversion temperature (PIT) method was introduced by Shinoda et al. supported the changes of solubility of polyoxyethylene-type surfactant with temperature. This surfactant becomes lipophilic with increase in temperature because of dehydration of polymer chain. But at low temperature, the surfactant monolayer features an oversized positive spontaneous curvature forming oil-swollen micellar solution phase [30].

2. Sonication method

Sonication method is another best because of prepare nanoemulsion. during this method the droplet size of conventional emulsion or maybe microemulsion are reduced with the help of sonication mechanism. This method isn't suitable for giant batches only small batches of nanoemulsion can be prepared by this method [31].

3. High homogenizer

This method is performed by applying a high over the system having oil phase, aqueous phase and surfactant or co-surfactant. The pressure is applied with the help of a special equipment know as homogenizer. There are some problems which are associated with homogenizer such as poor productivity, component deterioration because of difficult mass production and generation of much heat. With this method only oil in water (o/w) liquid nanoemulsion of but 20% oil phase are often prepared and cream nanoemulsion of high viscosity or hardness with a mean droplet diameter lower than 200 nm cannot be prepared [32].

CHARACTERIZATION OF NANOPARTICLES

Nano-emulsions aren't thermodynamically stable, and, due to that, their characteristics will depend upon preparation method. Here some parameters are discussed which should be analyzed at the time of preparation of nanoemulsion [33].

(i) Phase behaviour study: This study may be a characterization and optimization of ingredients (surfactant, oil phase and aqueous phase). Generally the study is important in case of nanoemulsion formulation prepared by phase inversion temperature method and self emulsification method in order to determine the phase of nanoemulsion and dispersibility. Study is completed by placing the different ingredients of nanoemulsion by varying the concentration in glass ampules and thoroughly homogenized at a certain temperature for a time until equilibrium. Anisotropic phase are often identified by polarized light.

(ii) Particle Size Analysis: Formulated nanoemulsion should be analyzed for his or her hydrodynamic particle size and particle size distribution. Generally just in case of nanoemulsion dynamic light scattering (DLS) method are used for the measurement of particles and further particle size distribution.

(iii) Surface charge measurement: Surface zeta potential of nanoemulsion droplets should be measured with the assistance of mini electrode to predict the surface properties of nanoemulsion.

(iv) Transmission microscopy (TEM): This method is used to observe the morphology in the nanoemulsion.

(v) Drug contain: This method is employed to determine the amount of drug contained in the formulation. Various methods (especially Western Blot method) are utilized in this order.

(vi) Viscosity: Viscosity should be measured to make sure the better delivery of the formulation.

NANOEMULSION INSTABILITY.

The instability of nanoemulsion is thanks to some main factors including creaming [34] flocculation [35, 36], coalescence[37] and Ostwald ripening [38]. Among them ostwald ripening is that the main mechanism of nanoemulsion instability because rest of the problem are minimized by the small size of nanoemulsion and use of nonionic type of surfactant. Creaming of nanoemulsion is prevented by the faster diffusion rate of smaller droplets. Vanderwall force is responsible for the attraction of droplets and results in the flocculation of emulsion. But just in case of nanoemulsion nonionic surfactant, it doesn't create any kind of attractive force, hence no flocculation occurs. The droplet size of nanoemulsion also prevent the flocculation because these small droplets show high curvature and laplace pressure opposes the deformation of huge droplets [39].Coalescence of droplets of nanoemulsion are often prevented by a thick multilamellar surfactant film adsorbed over the interface of droplets [40].

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